

Mental Health in the US Correctional System

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Abstract— Mental health in correctional systems has drawn growing attention due to the high prevalence of psychological disorders among incarcerated populations. This study examines the relationship between mental health disorders and disciplinary actions among male and female inmates. Using data from the 2016 Survey of Prison Inmates, the study found that inmates with mental health conditions were more likely to receive disciplinary sanctions than those without such conditions. Findings revealed that inmates with mental health disorders were more likely to face disciplinary actions while incarcerated. Additionally, when gender was considered, both men and women with mental health issues experienced higher rates of discipline, though the effect was greater among women. These results indicate that mental health history and gender influence institutional behavior and correctional responses. Overall, the findings suggest that implementing mental health programs, therapy, and counseling could help reduce disciplinary actions among inmates. Training correctional staff to recognize how inmates respond to institutional rules may improve outcomes.

Keywords—mental health, disciplinary actions, gender disparity

I. INTRODUCTION

Mental health in correctional systems is a critical area of study that examines how inmates with mental health issues or conditions experience incarceration compared to those without such conditions. Correctional environments are often rigid, demanding, and stressful, which can make it difficult for individuals with mental health issues or conditions to comply with institutional expectations. These difficulties may result in disciplinary actions such as segregation or solitary confinement, practices that can further heighten emotional distress and reinforce behavioral challenges [1].

The relationship between mental health and disciplinary outcomes is complex and may be influenced by gender. Research suggests that men and women display and manage psychological strain differently, which can affect both their conduct and how correctional staff interpret their behavior [2, 3]. Understanding these gendered differences is essential to

evaluating whether disciplinary responses reflect intentional rule-breaking or reactions to psychological distress linked to underlying mental health conditions.

Building on this context, the present research serves as a preliminary and exploratory study that investigates whether inmates with mental health issues or conditions are more likely to receive disciplinary actions than those without such conditions, and whether this relationship varies by gender. The goal is to identify general patterns and associations that can inform future, more comprehensive research, and contribute to the development of fair and effective correctional policies.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. General Overview of Mental Health Issues in Prison

Mental health challenges within correctional facilities are often intertwined with behavioral difficulties that can lead to disciplinary measures, including solitary confinement, confinement to own cell, higher custody level within facility, loss of privileges, and transferred to another facility [3]. Although disciplinary actions are intended to maintain institutional order and enforce compliance [4], they can have unintended consequences for inmates with mental health conditions. Individuals with psychological disorders frequently struggle to adapt to the rigid structure of prison life, where institutional policies and procedures may intensify their symptoms [2]. Practices such as strip searches, the use of restraints, and isolation can further amplify emotional distress, leaving inmates with preexisting conditions particularly vulnerable to additional psychological strain.

Mental health issues among inmates in correctional facilities may also cause inmates to be denied or not receive proper medical care. The lack of adequate care may lead to disciplinary actions that stem from untreated mental health issues rather than from intentional misconduct. Because correctional officers typically receive limited training on mental health, they may struggle to recognize behavioral symptoms associated with mental health issues. Consequently,

it becomes difficult for them to distinguish between deliberate rule violations and representations of mental illness [5].

Furthermore, inmates with mental disorders may struggle to follow institutional rules and are therefore more likely to be seen as disobedient [3]. As a result, they often face negative consequences and have an increased likelihood of being transferred to other facilities for disciplinary actions [5]. Ultimately, addressing the mental health needs of inmates is not only essential to mitigate behavioral and disciplinary challenges but also critical to promoting fairness, rehabilitation, and ethical responsibility within the correctional system.

B. Mistreatment of Mental Health Disorder

Behavioral symptoms, institutional rules, and stigma each play a key role in the relationship between mental health and disciplinary actions within correctional systems [1]. Offenders with mental health disorders often lack external support systems and experience isolation, which may lead to defiant or rule-breaking behavior as inmates attempt to cope or regain control. Adjusting to incarceration is particularly difficult, and studies have shown that inmates with mental health symptoms are more likely to commit serious infractions compared to those without such conditions [6]. The humiliation and stress associated with adapting to an unfamiliar environment may further amplify these behavioral challenges.

Rule violations often result in disciplinary measures, such as solitary confinement, that are intended to maintain institutional order. However, offenders who struggle to integrate into the correctional environment may rely on maladaptive coping strategies, including aggression, withdrawal, or self-harm. Individuals with disorders such as depression or psychosis are particularly vulnerable to such behaviors, which frequently lead to additional disciplinary sanctions [5]. These patterns reflect a cycle in which emotional strain and institutional control reinforce one another, escalating behavioral difficulties rather than resolving them.

Agnew's General Strain Theory (1992) offers a useful conceptual lens for understanding these dynamics. The theory posits that individuals engage in maladaptive or deviant behaviors when they experience significant strain, particularly when negative stimuli evoke emotions such as anger, frustration, or fear, and when effective coping mechanisms are unavailable. Within correctional settings, inmates with mental health disorders are especially susceptible to these processes. Chronic exposure to stressors such as overcrowding, victimization, and coercive supervision can generate intense emotional strain, leading to reactive or noncompliant behavior [1]. Although the present study did not directly apply or test this theory, it provides a valuable framework for interpreting how emotional strain and psychological distress may increase the likelihood of disciplinary actions among mentally ill inmates.

Stigma further compounds these challenges. Inmates with mental health conditions are often labeled as "dangerous" or "unstable," reinforcing negative stereotypes and prompting discriminatory responses from staff and peers [3]. These perceptions can result in increased surveillance, harsher disciplinary measures, and placement in segregation units

intended for control rather than treatment, which may heighten isolation and impede rehabilitation [5]. Gender differences also shape how incarcerated individuals cope with these stressors: women are more likely to internalize their distress, exhibiting depression or withdrawal, whereas men tend to respond with aggression or defiance [6].

C. Gender Differences in Mental Health

Gender differences play a critical role in shaping how inmates experience and respond to psychological strain within correctional environments. Women are more likely to internalize distress, displaying symptoms such as depression or withdrawal, while men tend to externalize strain through aggression or defiance [6]. These patterns align with the principles of General Strain Theory, suggesting that gendered emotional expression and coping strategies influence the pathway from psychological strain to institutional misconduct. Research consistently shows that inmates with mental health disorders, regardless of gender, are more vulnerable to victimization than those without such conditions [7].

However, men and women cope with these experiences differently. Men with mental health issues are more likely to face disciplinary sanctions, while women tend to respond to institutional stress through sadness and withdrawal [6]. Celinska and Sung (2016) further observed that female inmates experience institutional stressors more acutely than men, particularly those serving medium- to long-term sentences, who often accumulate more disciplinary actions. Elevated rates of victimization among women may also contribute to perceptions of noncompliance and difficulty adhering to institutional rules [2, 7].

Mental health symptoms further increase the risk of both victimization and disciplinary measures, including solitary confinement [8]. Male inmates with mental health conditions are especially likely to be placed in solitary confinement, whether for safety, behavioral adjustment, or contraband-related reasons [8]. Additionally, men commit more rule violations per month than women and are involved in a wider range of misconduct types [9].

Overall, these findings highlight significant gender differences in behavioral responses, disciplinary outcomes, and institutional management of inmates with mental health disorders. They suggest that both psychological and institutional factors interact with gender to shape how misconduct is displayed, interpreted, and sanctioned within correctional systems.

Drawing from the existing literature and theoretical perspectives, the current study seeks to examine the relationship between mental health status and disciplinary outcomes within correctional settings. Prior research suggests that inmates with mental health disorders are at greater risk of disciplinary sanctions due to heightened emotional strain, institutional stressors, and limited coping resources [1, 3, 6]. Furthermore, studies indicate that this relationship may differ by gender, as men and women exhibit distinct coping styles and behavioral responses to psychological strain [2, 10]. Based on this body of research, two hypotheses are proposed:

- H1: Inmates with mental health disorders are more likely to receive disciplinary actions compared to inmates without mental health disorders.
- H2: The relationship between mental health status and disciplinary actions varies by gender.

III. METHODS

The current study is a preliminary and exploratory analysis designed to examine patterns of mental health and disciplinary actions among incarcerated individuals using data from the Survey of Prison Inmates (SPI), 2016. The purpose of this pilot study is to provide an initial exploration of how mental health conditions are associated with inmates' involvement in institutional disciplinary actions, and whether these relationships differ by gender. Because this is a pilot study, the analysis focuses on identifying general patterns and associations rather than drawing causal conclusions.

A. Data and Sample

This study used data from the Survey of Prison Inmates (SPI), conducted by the Bureau of Justice Statistics (BJS). The dataset was distributed by the Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR 37692) and comprises a comprehensive national collection of information on individuals incarcerated in both state and federal correctional facilities (BJS, 2024). The SPI was designed to provide a detailed understanding of the characteristics, backgrounds, and experiences of inmates within the United States prison system.

The dataset includes responses from 24,848 inmates and captures a wide range of demographic variables, including age, gender, race, educational background, and offense type. In addition to these demographic measures, the survey gathers extensive information on inmates' behavioral patterns, criminal histories, institutional experiences, and interactions within correctional environments. This combination of demographic and behavioral data enables in-depth analysis of patterns and relationships across various aspects of incarceration, supporting a deeper understanding of the social and institutional dynamics of the prison population.

B. Dependent Variable: Disciplinary Action

The measurement of disciplinary action in this study was based on 13 questions from the SPI (2024). These questions identify specific disciplinary responses inmates received for their most recent rule of violation while incarcerated. Each variable captures whether an inmate experienced a particular form of punishment or institutional consequence. The following lists indicate questions used to form a disciplinary action variable: (1) Solitary Confinement or Segregation; (2) Confinement to Own Cell or Quarters; (3) Higher Custody Level Within Facility; (4) Transferred to Another Facility; (5) Loss of "Good/Gain" Time or "Bad" Time; (6) Received a New Sentence; (7) Given Extra Work; (8) Loss or Change of Work Assignment; (9) Loss of Privileges (including commissary or visiting privileges); (10) Put in Restraints; (11) Received Formal Reprimand Only; (12) Received No Punishment or Punishment Suspended; and (13) Other Disciplinary Action.

Each of these questions asked respondents whether the corresponding disciplinary action was taken for their most recent institutional violation. For this study, these 13 questions were used to generate a single binary variable indicating whether an inmate had been subject to any disciplinary action. Inmates who answered "Yes" to any one of the thirteen items were coded as "1" (indicating they had been engaged in disciplinary action), while those who answered "No" to all items were coded as "0" (indicating no disciplinary action). This binary variable was generated to simplify analysis and facilitate interpretation during the pilot study phase, providing a clear, inclusive indicator of whether inmates had experienced any form of institutional discipline.

C. Independent Variable: Mental Health

The measurement of mental health in this study was based on seven questions from the SPI (2024). These questions captured inmates' self-reported histories of mental health diagnoses made by a medical doctor or a mental health professional. The following lists indicate questions used to form a mental health variable: (1) whether an inmate had ever been told they had manic depression, bipolar disorder, or mania; (2) whether an inmate had ever been told they had a depressive disorder; (3) whether an inmate had ever been told they had schizophrenia or another psychotic disorder; (4) whether an inmate had ever been told they had post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD); (5) whether an inmate had ever been told they had an anxiety disorder, such as panic disorder or obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD); (6) whether an inmate had ever been told they had a personality disorder, such as antisocial or borderline personality disorder; and (7) whether an inmate had ever been told they had another mental or emotional condition not previously specified.

For this study, the seven questions were used to generate a binary variable indicating whether an inmate had any mental health condition. Inmates who answered "Yes" to any one of the seven items were coded as "1" (indicating the presence of a mental health condition), while those who answered "No" to all seven items were coded as "0" (indicating no reported mental health condition). This binary variable was created to simplify the analysis process and facilitate interpretation during the pilot study phase, providing a clear and inclusive indicator of whether inmates had been diagnosed with any form of mental or emotional disorder.

D. Control Variable: Gender

Gender was included as a control variable in the analysis. Although the dataset contains a wide range of demographic, behavioral, and institutional control variables, such as age, education level, race, offense type, and sentence length, this study was designed as a pilot and exploratory analysis. Therefore, only gender was included as a control variable to maintain analytical focus and simplicity while providing an initial understanding of the relationship between mental health and other study variables.

E. Analysis

The analysis for this study employed logistic regression to examine the relationship between mental health status and involvement in disciplinary actions among incarcerated individuals. Because both the mental health and disciplinary action variables were binary, logistic regression was the most appropriate statistical method for estimating the probability of inmates engaging in or being subjected to disciplinary actions based on their reported mental health conditions. Logistic regression is widely used in social science research to model dichotomous outcomes and assess the strength and direction of associations among predictors [11].

The first model examined the overall association between mental health status and disciplinary action to determine whether inmates who reported a mental health condition were more likely to have experienced disciplinary sanctions. The second model introduced gender as a control variable to explore whether this relationship differed between male and female inmates. Including gender in the model allowed for an assessment of potential gender-based differences in how mental health relates to institutional behavior and disciplinary outcomes. This stepwise analytical approach provided both a general understanding of the association between mental health and disciplinary involvement and a more nuanced perspective on how gender may influence or moderate that relationship.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The initial logistic regression model examined the association between prior mental health diagnosis and involvement in disciplinary action among inmates. Results indicate that inmates with a prior record were significantly more likely to be involved in disciplinary incidents compared to those without a record (OR = 1.55, $p < 0.001$). This suggests that individuals who had prior mental health issues faced approximately 55 percent higher odds of disciplinary action while incarcerated.

The constant term (OR = 0.31) represents the baseline odds of disciplinary action for inmates without a prior record. The overall model was statistically significant (LR $\chi^2 = 237.34$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that prior record status meaningfully predicts institutional disciplinary outcomes. However, the pseudo- R^2 value (0.0081) suggests that prior record alone explains only a small portion of the variation in disciplinary behavior. This finding underscores that while an initial mental health record is an essential factor, other variables may also likely contribute to differences in inmates' disciplinary experiences.

TABLE 1. Logistic Regression Predicting Involvement in Disciplinary Action with Mental Health Status

Predictor	Odds Ratio	Std. Error	z	p-value	95% CI*
Mental Health	1.55	0.04	15.39	0.000	[1.47, 1.64]
Constant	0.31	0.01	-58.46	0.000	[0.30, 0.32]
LR χ^2 (1) = 237.34, $p < 0.001$; Pseudo $R^2 = 0.0081$; $N = 24,848$					

Note: *CI indicates Confidence Interval.

The second analysis examined the association between gender, mental health status, and their interaction in predicting disciplinary action among inmates (See Table 2). Both gender and mental health status independently increased the likelihood of disciplinary involvement. Specifically, male inmates were about 1.5 times more likely than female inmates to be involved in disciplinary actions ($p < 0.001$), and inmates with a diagnosed mental health condition were roughly twice as likely to experience disciplinary sanctions compared to those without a mental health diagnosis ($p < 0.001$).

TABLE 2. Logistic Regression Predicting Involvement in Disciplinary Action by Gender and Mental Health Status

Predictor	Odds Ratio	Std. Error	z	p-value	95% CI*
Male (vs. Female)	1.53	0.09	6.93	0.000	[1.36, 1.73]
Mental Health Condition (vs. None)	2.08	0.14	10.93	0.000	[1.82, 2.37]
Male \times Mental Health Condition	0.74	0.06	-4.02	0.000	[0.64, 0.86]
Constant	0.21	0.01	-26.65	0.000	[0.19, 0.24]
*LR χ^2 (3) = 298.05, $p < 0.001$; Pseudo $R^2 = 0.0102$; $N = 24,848$					

However, having a mental health condition increases the likelihood of disciplinary action for both men and women, but the effect is more substantial for women (OR = 0.74, $p < 0.001$). Women without a mental health diagnosis have relatively low odds of disciplinary involvement, but those with a mental health condition are nearly twice as likely to face disciplinary action. For men, the increase in risk associated with mental health conditions is smaller, largely because men already have a higher baseline likelihood of disciplinary action even without a diagnosis. This finding suggests that mental health challenges are particularly consequential for female inmates in shaping their experiences of institutional discipline.

As Simes and colleagues (2022) found in their study, the present preliminary research also identified a significant relationship between mental health issues and the likelihood of disciplinary actions among inmates. Consistent with their findings, this study observed that inmates with mental health problems were more likely to receive disciplinary actions. However, unlike Simes et al. (2022), the purpose of this research was to establish the presence of this relationship rather than to examine the mechanisms explaining it.

Simes et al. (2022) suggest that inmates with mental health symptoms may struggle to respond appropriately to institutional cues or commands due to cognitive difficulties and mood instability, which can increase the risk of misconduct. Similarly, environmental stressors such as overcrowding, inadequate living conditions, and limited autonomy can heighten psychological distress and provoke reactive behaviors [2]. These findings imply that both psychological and environmental factors likely contribute to the observed correlation, although they were beyond the scope of the current study.

The results of this study also revealed a meaningful gender disparity in disciplinary outcomes. Female inmates with mental health issues were more likely than both male inmates and females without mental health conditions to receive disciplinary actions, suggesting that institutional responses may differ according to both gender and mental health status. While men with mental health issues were also sanctioned, the differences between those with and without such conditions were relatively small. This pattern indicates that mental health plays a more pronounced role in shaping disciplinary outcomes for women than for men, aligning with prior research showing that women's emotional and behavioral expressions are more likely to draw formal disciplinary responses [8].

Although women generally commit fewer serious infractions than men, those with mental health issues often accumulate more disciplinary actions over time, possibly due to heightened scrutiny and differential enforcement within correctional environments [6]. Furthermore, women tend to internalize distress through sadness and depression, whereas men more often externalize it through anger and aggression [11]. These gendered differences in coping and staff perception may help explain the disparities observed in this study and underscore the importance of gender-responsive approaches to managing inmate behavior and mental health in future correctional research and policy.

The findings suggest that inmates with mental health issues are disciplined at a higher rate within correctional facilities. When gender is considered, there was a pattern shown from mental health history that females were more impacted than males. Female inmates with a mental health record have nearly double the chance of discipline compared to females without one. Additionally, the study points out that gender differences shape how inmates respond to stressors in the facilities, men tend to act out aggressively and receive harsh punishments, while women internalize distress and face victimization [11]. The results suggest that mental health history is an important factor in disciplinary outcomes, but its influence varies by gender.

Overall, future research should investigate mental health programs, therapy, and counseling as a way to reduce disciplinary among inmates. Although correctional staff lack training to provide mental health care, there should be more effective ways to become more aware of how inmates respond to rules [5]. Similarly, exploring gender specific programs to help inmates cope with adjustments into prison environments [12]. Assessing how correctional staff perceive gender and mental health influence on disciplinary decisions.

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Hannahrae Lee, Associate Professor of Criminal Justice and Cybersecurity. Tiana is a first-generation student who wants to highlight the importance of mental health in prison settings. Tiana has a dedicated interest in attending a master's program for mental health counseling to become a Licensed Mental Health Clinician, in order to give back to her community and offer the resources needed to grow and heal. Tiana is also a poet and loves to sing and dance.